

Some New Reactions of Fusible and Infusible White Precipitates of Mercury and Their Constitution.

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In spite of numerous investigations, the constitution of fusible and infusible white precipitates of mercury was not very clear for a long time till Franklin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 27, 820; 1907, 29, 35), from a study of reactions in liquid ammonia and of sodamide on mercuric chloride, produced strong evidences in support of Hofmann and Marburg's view (*Annalen*, 1899, 305, 191; *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1905, 46, 25). Franklin's view about the constitution of these compounds has thus been generally accepted. According to this the infusible white precipitate is regarded as an ammonolysed or ammonobasic compound $H_2N-HgCl$ and the fusible white precipitate as a molecular compound containing ammonia of crystallisation being represented by $HgCl_2 \cdot 2NH_3$. A large number of facts argue in favour of this view. These have already been discussed by Hofmann and Franklin and need not be detailed here. With a view to further test the validity of this theory we studied the reactions of these bodies with certain reactive substances which were likely to throw some light on their constitution. The results obtained are discussed in the present paper.

Action of Ammoniacal Hydrogen Peroxide upon Infusible and Fusible White Precipitates.

Ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide was found to readily reduce the infusible white precipitate to metallic mercury. The filtrate, after the reaction with hydrogen peroxide, was free from mercury, but contained a large amount of ammonium chloride. An intermediate yellow product was obtained before the reduction to mercury commenced; this was believed to be chloride of Millon's base admixed with mercuric oxide and it gave metallic mercury on ignition.

Fusible white precipitate behaved towards hydrogen peroxide in a similar manner, but the reaction was somewhat slower.

Mercuric oxide also behaves in an exactly analogous way towards ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide.

These reactions are best explained if we assume that the same reduction reaction is involved in all these cases; that is, it is the mercuric oxide on which alone the hydrogen peroxide acts. It is well-known that the hydrolysis of infusible white precipitate follows according to the following equation:

Further hydrolysis leads to the formation of mercuric oxide.

The ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide then acts upon the mercuric oxide reducing it to metallic mercury. The equilibrium is thus disturbed and the whole of the substance is ultimately reduced.

The formation of the ultimate products, mercuric oxide and ammonium chloride by the hydrolysis of the infusible white precipitate argues strongly in favour of its constitution as a substituted ammonium chloride—its hydrolysis being then easily explained as follows:—

The formation of the intermediate product, the chloride of Million's base may be regarded as due to the action of mercuric oxide upon the infusible white precipitate, thus:

Action of Ethyl Mercaptan upon the Infusible and the Fusible White Precipitates.

Perfectly dry infusible white precipitate was treated with an alcoholic solution of ethyl mercaptan under reflux on the water-bath. A small amount of free ammonia was liberated with slight evolution of heat. After some time bright colourless leaflets began to separate when the mixture was cooled and filtered. These were then

fractionally recrystallized and ultimately obtained in three different fractions *a*, *b* and *c*.

Fraction (*a*) forms bright leaflets soluble in hot alcohol with a sharp m.p. at 76°. It was found to contain only Hg, S, C and H and was free from chlorine and nitrogen. It was decomposed by acids with formation of diethylsulphide. On dry ignition it gave mercuric sulphide, diethyl sulphide and metallic mercury. (Found: Hg, 61.95. $\text{Hg}(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_5)_2$ requires Hg, 62 per cent.).

$\text{Hg}(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_5)_2$ melts at 76°. So the product is mercury mercaptide.

Fraction (*b*) formed infusible bright leaflets insoluble in water. It was found to contain Hg, S, Cl, C and H and was free from nitrogen. It gave mercuric sulphide, calomel and ethyl sulphide on dry ignition. (Found: Hg, 67.4. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{S.HgCl}$ requires Hg, 67.5 per cent.). The substance is therefore mercury chloromercaptide.

Fraction (*c*) was highly soluble in water and was found on examination to be pure ammonium chloride.

Fraction (*a*) was obtained in the largest quantity, the yield of the fraction (*b*) being the smallest.

Similar results were obtained when the fusible white precipitate was acted upon by ethyl mercaptan. But in this case the yield of chloromercaptide was fairly large.

The results indicate clearly that the infusible white precipitate can act both as a substituted ammonia and as a substituted ammonium chloride. In the first case the chlorine atom remains attached to the mercury and in the second it is held under the influence of the nitrogen atom. Thus:—

The reaction with ethyl mercaptan then proceeds as follows:—

But as the yield of mercury mercaptide largely preponderates over that of the chloro-mercaptide it may be assumed that in this reaction the infusible white precipitate acts mostly as a substituted ammonium chloride having the constitution $[\text{H}_2\text{N}=\text{Hg}]\text{Cl}$.

The reaction in the case of the fusible white precipitate can be readily explained by assuming that the latter undergoes partial dissociation as represented below :

HgCl_2 reacting with the mercaptan gives chloromercaptide and $[\text{Hg.NH}_2]\text{Cl}$ gives mainly mercury mercaptide with a little chloromercaptide as already explained. Both the above two types of dissociation of the fusible precipitate proceed almost to an equal extent as it gives both mercury mercaptide and mercury chloromercaptide in about equal quantities when treated with ethyl mercaptan.

Action of Thiocarbamide upon Infusible White Precipitate.

When the infusible white precipitate was treated with an alcoholic solution of thiocarbamide, it at once turned black with evolution of a large amount of ammonia. After the reaction was complete, the residue was separated by filtration. The alcoholic filtrate on evaporation left a white crystalline mass. This was dissolved in water and treated with an excess of ammoniacal silver nitrate solution when a yellow precipitate was obtained. The ammoniacal filtrate on being acidified with nitric acid gave a white precipitate of silver chloride only. The white mass left after the evaporation of the alcohol gave ammonia with caustic soda solution. This proved that the alcoholic filtrate contained ammonium chloride. The yellow precipitate obtained by the addition of ammoniacal silver nitrate solution was dissolved in nitric acid, reprecipitated with dilute ammonia, washed and dried. On examination and analysis it was found to be the silver salt of cyanamide. (Found: Ag, 82.4. CN.NAg_2 requires Ag, 84.3 per cent.)

The black mass was found to be a mixture of mercuric sulphide and the double compound of mercuric chloride and thiocarbamide.

The same reaction takes place in aqueous solution also. So the action of thiocarbamide upon the infusible white precipitate results in the formation of mercuric sulphide, a double-compound of mercuric chloride and thiocarbamide, cyanamide, ammonia and ammonium chloride.

It is also well-known that mercuric oxide reacts with thiocarbamide forming mercuric sulphide and cyanamide.

As the chlorine of the infusible white precipitate appears partly as ammonium chloride and partly as mercuric chloride in the products of the reaction it may be assumed that it reacts here both as a substituted ammonia and substituted ammonium chloride. In other words it behaves as a mixture of $\text{H}_2\text{N}\cdot\text{HgCl}$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{N}=\text{Hg}]\text{Cl}$.

The reaction between thiocarbamide and the fusible white precipitate proceeds almost exactly in the same manner giving rise to the same products.

Action of Thiocarbamide upon White Precipitates.

An alcoholic solution of thiocarbamide was found to react readily with the infusible white precipitate without any evolution of ammonia. The products of reaction were black mercuric sulphide, and diphenyl guanidine hydrochloride. The latter was obtained by the evaporation of the alcoholic filtrate. The mechanism of the reaction is best explained by the following equation assuming the infusible white precipitate to be a substituted ammonium chloride.

(Cf. Forster, *Annalen*, 1875, 175, 35).

The fusible white precipitate reacts in a similar way with an alcoholic solution of thiocarbamide forming mercuric sulphide, diphenylguanidine hydrochloride and a little ammonium chloride.

As a result of the study of these reactions it may be concluded that the infusible white precipitate can under certain circumstances behave as a substituted ammonium chloride with the chlorine atom directly or indirectly linked to the nitrogen atom. But it is also well-known that the infusible white precipitate generally behaves as a substituted ammonia or as an ammono-basic mercuric chloride as has been established by Hofmann and Franklin. Hence we may now assume that the infusible white precipitate is an equilibrium mixture of these two types of molecules.

